

LEADERSHIP DYNAMICS AND EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN AGRITED NIGERIA LIMITED IBADAN, OYO STATE, NIGERIA

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Employee, Employee Engagement, Leaders, Leadership Dynamics, Transformational.

Abstract: *Employee engagement is essential to organisational success because engaged employees are committed to their work, aligned with organisational goals, and contribute positively to performance. Conversely, disengagement reduces productivity and profitability. This study explored leadership dynamics and employee engagement in AGRITED Nigeria Limited, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, using Social Exchange Theory (SET) framework. A descriptive survey research design was employed, and a sample size of 200 employees were selected using simple random sampling technique. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire and analysed using descriptive statistics. Findings showed that 69% of respondents were happy with their responsibilities, suggesting a positive attitude toward job roles. Also, 75% indicated that their jobs inspire them, demonstrating strong motivation. Additionally, 57.5% expressed willingness to put in extra effort to support organisational success. The study concluded that employee engagement and job satisfaction at AGRITED Nigeria Limited were largely influenced by effective leadership practices and positive workplace relationships. The study recommended that organizations should invest in leadership development programmes that equip managers with flexible leadership skills capable of meeting employee expectations and advancing organisational goals.*

Introduction

Employee engagement has always been essential to an organisation's success. It plays a vital role in increasing efficiency and output, boosting customers' loyalty and happiness, and enhancing the reputation of the company. In today's fast-paced business environment, organisations that put employee engagement first enjoy several

advantages, including increased productivity, growth, and competitiveness. One of the many factors that influence employee engagement is leadership dynamics. Leadership dynamics are essential to employee engagement because leaders' actions, decisions, and behaviors have a big impact on workers' commitment, motivation, and job satisfaction. As a result, organisations

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must implement successful leadership styles that will raise employee engagement, motivation, and dedication (Olabimitan & Adekoya, 2023). A higher degree of employee involvement within the company is thought to be a key factor in improved worker performance, which in turn contributes to organisational success. This prompted companies to offer job security to their staff in the past in order to increase employee engagement and productivity (Damisa & Zainol, 2022). Engaged workers who do various duties help organisations complete their work. Customer happiness, business success, and staff inventiveness can all be impacted by employee engagement. An engaged employee is of great value to the organisation as they may need little or no supervision to accomplish the tasks assigned to them (Salau et al., 2022; Arubayi, 2022; Ojeleye et al., 2023). Successful organisations rely on the high performance of their employees which is enhanced by their level of engagement. Engaged employees develop an attachment with the organisation and this leads to better organisational performance (Balogun & Zaghmout, 2024). The psychological concept of engagement goes well beyond satisfaction: engaged employees are enthusiastic about their work and dedicated to promoting the objectives of their organisation. They identify with the organisation's mission and values by representing their organisation even when they are not officially working; they take on the role of ambassadors, advocating the company's goals and principles both within and

outside the office. This degree of dedication to and identification with the organisation creates a pleasant work environment, which can enhance output, innovation, and the overall success of the organisation. Establishing a work environment that stimulates employee engagement and retention is a strategic advantage for organisations. This is because companies with lower employee turnover and higher employee engagement are more likely to achieve their objectives than those with higher employee turnover and disengagement (Arubayi, 2022). Therefore, having a workforce that is both interested in their work and retained inside the organisation is strategically crucial. This is seen as a positive factor directly influencing the organisation's ability to meet its overarching goals and objectives (Ojeleye et al., 2023). However, although organisations put fair compensation and promotion policies in place to make sure that talent is kept, these strategies seem to be enough to energize and keep employees, but they occasionally fail to generate the level of engagement needed to keep them committed (Olabimitan & Adekoya, 2023). Disengaged employees have a negative impact on business: it affects customer loyalty, job satisfaction, and performance in the workplace. Therefore, every organisation must strive to have a high level of employee engagement and ensure a good match between the employee and the job in order to achieve outstanding performance. They must understand that employees have their own personal wishes and obligations that need to

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be considered (Ojeleye et al., 2023). When employees are fully engaged, they become committed and attached emotionally to their work and the organisation, and are more likely to be motivated and productive. This will have a great effect on the performance of the organisation as a whole, as it will increase the level of job satisfaction, enhance their loyalty, and improve the retention rate of the employees. On the other hand, when employees are not engaged, the organisation suffers. Leadership style is a crucial factor that contributes to employee engagement. When an organisation has the right leadership style, employee engagement levels are likely to increase and employee performance is also enhanced, thereby leading to more productivity and achievement of organisational objectives (Salau et al., 2022). It is therefore important for organisations to make sure that the leadership style they employ enhances employee engagement because a leader's ability to motivate and empower employees helps them to feel a sense of belonging and responsibility towards the organization (Balogun & Zaghmout, 2024). Employee engagement is an essential aspect of leadership, and effective leaders have a great impact on this engagement. It is one of the organisation's top three challenges, listed by over half of Human Resource professionals, followed by succession planning, culture management, employee retention and turnover, and performance management (Olabimitan & Adekoya, 2023). When it comes to the

employee's work environment, leadership is a crucial situational aspect that will have a big impact on their psychology, attitudes, and conduct (Salau et al., 2022). In general, leadership style is the pattern of a leader's dealings both seen and unseen with subordinates. It is a constant combination of beliefs, skills, traits, and attitudes that trigger one's actions. It shows a leader's belief in the capabilities of their subordinates and represents the behaviour and strategy used by a leader to influence them (Saragih, 2023).

Statement of the Problem

Employee engagement is vital to achieving organizational goals, yet many organizations struggle with low levels of commitment and motivation among their workforce. Disengaged employees often lack enthusiasm, purpose, and connection to the organization's vision, resulting in low morale, reduced productivity, and high turnover. While numerous studies have explored the link between leadership and employee engagement across various sectors, limited attention has been given to livestock production companies in Nigeria. This study therefore seeks to examine how leadership dynamics influence employee engagement at AGRITED Nigeria Limited, Ibadan.

Research Objectives

- i. To find out the level of employee engagement in AGRITED Nigeria Limited;
- ii. To examine the influence of leadership dynamics on job satisfaction among employees in AGRITED Nigeria Limited.

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Research Questions

- i. What is the level of employee engagement in AGRITED Nigeria Limited?
- ii. What is the influence of leadership on job satisfaction among employees in AGRITED Nigeria Limited?

Literature Review

Employee Engagement

An engaged employee is one who is passionate about their work, emotionally invested in the company, and committed to its success. It is a desirable state that reflects concern for organizational goals, dedication, enthusiasm, focused effort, and both behavioral and attitudinal commitment (Okoro & Nwosu, 2022). Employee engagement goes beyond job satisfaction; it embodies a worker's positive emotions and deep sense of belonging to the organization (Adeola, 2023). An engaged employee uses their physical, emotional, and intellectual energy to perform effectively, contributing meaningfully to the realization of organizational objectives (Oluwole & Adebayo, 2024). The physical aspect of engagement relates to the energy employees exert in their roles, the emotional aspect concerns their feelings toward the job and emotional investment, while the intellectual aspect deals with alertness, curiosity, and mental focus (Eze & Hassan, 2021). Engaged employees willingly go beyond their job descriptions, take initiative, and embody the organization's culture and values (Olabisi &

Yusuf, 2023). They believe in their capacity to make a difference, aligning their personal goals with those of the organization. Engagement influences attitudes, reduces absenteeism and turnover, and enhances performance, showing a strong correlation between engagement and overall organizational productivity (Okafor & Aina, 2025).

Employee engagement is a global concept measured differently across fields but universally recognized as vital to organizational success (Ogunleye & Okon, 2021). It integrates organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and employees' intention to remain with their employer to create a motivated and high-performing workforce (Eboh & Aderemi, 2022). Although engagement drivers may differ across industries, they are largely rooted in human factors such as trust, loyalty, dedication, and inspiration (Ibrahim & Chukwu, 2023). Highly engaged employees are more motivated and happier, leading to improved individual, team, and organizational performance (Omotayo, 2024). Consequently, an organization's ability to engage and retain its workforce contributes significantly to its competitiveness, productivity, and profitability (Adeola, 2023; Okafor & Aina, 2025).

Job Satisfaction

The level of satisfaction an employee derives from a job largely depends on their perception of their position, workplace environment, compensation, and benefits, all of which directly influence performance (Akinbo, 2023; Judge,

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Weiss, Kammeyer-Mueller, & Hulin, 2017). Job satisfaction is a positive emotional state that arises from evaluating one's job attributes and the sense of fulfillment derived from performing work-related tasks (Spector, 1997; Akinbo, 2022). It encompasses several factors, including the nature of work, the work environment, relationships with colleagues and supervisors, as well as opportunities for growth, achievement, and development (Herzberg, Mausner, & Snyderman, 1959; Akinbo, 2021). Employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to be more motivated, committed, and engaged in their roles (Judge, Thoresen, Bono, & Patton, 2001; Akinbo, 2024). Organisations that prioritize job satisfaction are more likely to experience higher retention rates, improved productivity, and a more positive organisational culture, as contented employees contribute actively to achieving corporate goals

(Robbins&Judge,2019;Akinbo,2023).

Identifying and addressing issues that affect employee satisfaction is essential for formulating effective human resource policies that strengthen organisational performance (Armstrong & Taylor, 2021; Akinbo, 2023). Research has consistently shown a strong link between job satisfaction and employee engagement, with findings indicating that satisfied employees are more likely to be engaged workers (Harter, Schmidt, & Hayes, 2002; Saks, 2006; Akinbo, 2025). Employees are naturally inclined to contribute to organisational success and seek meaning in their work (Kahn, 1990;

Akinbo, 2024). Therefore, workplace practices that foster meaningful engagement, recognition, and professional growth not only enhance employee commitment but also positively influence overall job satisfaction and organisational outcomes (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008; Schaufeli, 2013; Akinbo, 2025).

Leadership Dynamics and Employee Engagement

Employee engagement serves as an essential metric for assessing organisational and leadership performance, as higher levels of engagement indicate stronger relationships between leaders and employees, a stable work environment, and greater creativity and innovation (Harter et al., 2002; Schaufeli, 2013; Akinbo, 2023). Engaged employees are motivated by reliable leaders who encourage commitment to organisational growth and success (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008; Oladimeji & Adebayo, 2022). According to the ISO 9001:2015 standard, employee engagement involves fostering motivation, active participation, and involvement in organisational processes to enhance productivity (International Organization for Standardization, 2015). While motivation drives specific tasks, engagement encompasses emotional energy, cognitive focus, and consistent effort (Kahn, 1990; Macey & Schneider, 2008). Recent studies in Nigeria revealed that employee engagement significantly reduces burnout, promotes job satisfaction, and sustains long-term loyalty among public and private sector workers (Akinbo, 2023; Eze &

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Chukwu, 2021). Engagement is shaped by employees' understanding of their roles, desire for improvement, and adherence to organisational values (Truss et al., 2013). It represents a stable emotional and behavioural state that determines how employees relate to their work over time (Rich et al., 2010). The relationship between leadership dynamics and employee engagement has become increasingly significant in modern organisations, where flexible leadership is essential for adapting to changing workforce expectations (Yukl, 2013; Okoro & Adebayo, 2024). Organisational identification and engagement are closely linked to perceived organisational support and leadership style (Eisenberger et al., 2002; Macey & Schneider, 2008). Consistent use of effective leadership approaches enhances employee motivation, commitment, and performance (Avolio et al., 2009; Akinbo, 2023). Transformational leaders, in particular, inspire trust, empowerment, and higher engagement (Bass & Riggio, 2006), while people-oriented leadership that values respect and collaboration results in stronger organisational loyalty (Northouse, 2019; Oyetunde & Aremu, 2021). Positive leadership behaviours improve employees' mental well-being and productivity, reinforcing engagement as a key indicator of leadership effectiveness and organisational success (Breevaart et al., 2014; Akinbo, 2023). Consequently, leadership styles such as transformational, transactional, and participative directly influence employees'

attitudes, satisfaction, and willingness to remain committed to the organisation (Judge & Piccolo, 2004; Avolio & Yammarino, 2013; Eze & Chukwu, 2021).

Theoretical Review

Social Exchange Theory

The Social Exchange Theory posits that social behaviour results from an exchange process aimed at maximizing benefits and minimizing costs (Homans, 1958). It assumes that individuals naturally seek rewards and avoid punishments in their interactions, striving for outcomes that yield maximum gain and minimal loss. Crossman (1966) explained this relationship through the formula: Behaviour (Profit) = Interaction Benefits – Interaction Costs, implying that actions are more likely to occur when rewards outweigh penalties. Homans (1958), in his work *Social Behaviour as Exchange*, emphasized that social interactions involve the exchange of both tangible and intangible resources—such as time, effort, approval, money, power, and status—between individuals. This reciprocity-based concept illustrates that relationships persist when benefits exceed costs and dissolve when the reverse occurs. In organizational settings, leaders who practice fairness, show appreciation, and recognize employee contributions cultivate trust and loyalty (Blau, 1964; Emerson, 1976). Employees, in turn, reciprocate with higher commitment, engagement, and performance. When leaders involve subordinates in decision-making and provide opportunities for growth,

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they reinforce the cycle of mutual benefit and trust (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005).

The relevance of the Social Exchange Theory to this study lies in its explanation of how leadership dynamics influence employee engagement at AGRITED Nigeria Limited. The theory provides a framework for understanding the reciprocal relationship between leaders and employees—where positive leadership behaviours, such as fairness, recognition, and support, generate trust, loyalty, and engagement. Transformational leadership, in particular, aligns closely with this theory, as it focuses on motivating employees through inspiration, empowerment, and individualized consideration, thereby fostering mutual respect and commitment (Settoon, Bennett & Liden, 1996). In contrast, transactional leadership emphasizes reward-based exchanges that directly reflect the principles of social exchange, while laissez faire leadership may weaken this reciprocal bond due to lack of interaction. Therefore, Social Exchange Theory is relevant to this study as it helps explain how different leadership styles can either strengthen or diminish employee engagement through the balance of perceived benefits and costs in leader-employee relationships.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of Level of Employee Engagement Statements

Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I am happy with my current responsibilities in my organisation.	48 (24.0)	138 (69.0)	11 (5.5)	3 (1.5)

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive research design. This design was chosen because it focuses on obtaining facts, opinions, attitudes, and behaviors of respondents in relation to the study objectives. Data were gathered from the staff of AGRITED Nigeria Limited using a semi-structured questionnaire. The population comprised four hundred and two (402) employees of AGRITED Nigeria Limited, selected as a leading firm in the livestock production industry. Taro Yamane formula was used to determine a sample size of two hundred (200) respondents, providing a reliable representation of the population. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pre-test was conducted on 10% of the population in a similar organization, and the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.72 confirmed internal consistency, face content validity was adopted. Data collected were analyzed through inferential and descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, and standard deviation employed to summarize demographic information and response patterns, using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.

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My job inspires me.	40 (20.0)	150 (75.0)	8 (4.0)	2 (1.0)
I am willing to put in extra effort to help my organisation succeed.	24 (12.0)	115 (57.5)	42 (21.0)	19 (9.5)
I feel valued at my workplace.	20 (10.0)	92 (46.0)	68 (34.0)	20 (10.0)
I see a future for myself at my organisation.	21 (10.5)	76 (38.0)	80 (40.0)	23 (11.5)
The leadership style in my organisation enhances employee engagement.	23 (11.5)	118 (59.0)	37 (18.5)	22 (11.0)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis of responses on employee engagement at AGRITED Nigeria Limited reveals that a significant proportion of employees expressed positive perceptions toward their work and leadership. For the statement “I am happy with my current responsibilities in my organisation,” 48 respondents (24.0%) strongly agreed, 138 (69.0%) agreed, 11 (5.5%) disagreed, and 3 (1.5%) strongly disagreed, showing that most employees are satisfied with their job roles. Regarding “My job inspires me,” 40 respondents (20.0%) strongly agreed, 150 (75.0%) agreed, 8 (4.0%) disagreed, and 2 (1.0%) strongly disagreed, indicating that the majority find their work motivating. On the statement “I am willing to put in extra effort to help my organisation succeed,” 24 respondents (12.0%) strongly agreed, 115 (57.5%) agreed, 42 (21.0%) disagreed, and 19 (9.5%) strongly disagreed, suggesting that while many employees are

dedicated, a noticeable portion are less motivated to go beyond their assigned tasks. For “I feel valued at my workplace,” 20 respondents (10.0%) strongly agreed, 92 (46.0%) agreed, 68 (34.0%) disagreed, and 20 (10.0%) strongly disagreed, implying that almost half of the workforce feels undervalued. Concerning “I see a future for myself at my organisation,” 21 respondents (10.5%) strongly agreed, 76 (38.0%) agreed, 80 (40.0%) disagreed, and 23 (11.5%) strongly disagreed, reflecting uncertainty among employees about long-term career prospects. Lastly, for “The leadership style in my organisation enhances employee engagement,” 23 respondents (11.5%) strongly agreed, 118 (59.0%) agreed, 37 (18.5%) disagreed, and 22 (11.0%) strongly disagreed, showing that while most employees view leadership positively, there remains a segment that feels leadership practices could be improved to strengthen engagement.

Table 2: Descriptive analysis of leadership dynamics (transformational, transactional, laissez-faire leadership style) on job satisfaction

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Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I feel a sense of accomplishment from my work tasks.	33 (16.5)	125 (62.5)	25 (12.5)	17 (8.5)
My supervisor encourages innovative thinking.	35 (17.5)	126 (63.0)	22 (11.0)	17 (8.5)
I am satisfied with the level of recognition for my contributions under my supervisor's leadership.	32 (16.0)	95 (47.5)	57 (28.5)	16 (8.0)
My supervisor provides guidance without pressure.	23 (11.5)	121 (60.5)	35 (17.5)	21 (10.5)
Under my supervisor's leadership, I perform my work voluntarily.	23 (11.5)	128 (64.0)	28 (14.0)	21 (10.5)
My supervisor's leadership style has impacted my overall job satisfaction.	28 (14.0)	123 (61.5)	26 (13.0)	23 (11.5)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The data presented on leadership influence and employee motivation at AGRITED Nigeria Limited indicates generally positive perceptions toward supervisory practices, though some areas reveal moderate dissatisfaction. For the statement “I feel a sense of accomplishment from my work tasks,” 33 respondents (16.5%) strongly agreed, 125 (62.5%) agreed, 25 (12.5%) disagreed, and 17 (8.5%) strongly disagreed, suggesting that most employees derive fulfillment from their job tasks. On “My supervisor encourages innovative thinking,” 35 respondents (17.5%) strongly agreed, 126 (63.0%) agreed, 22 (11.0%) disagreed, and 17 (8.5%) strongly disagreed, showing that the majority believe their supervisors promote creativity and innovation. Regarding “I am satisfied with the level of recognition for my contributions under my supervisor's leadership,”

32 respondents (16.0%) strongly agreed, 95 (47.5%) agreed, 57 (28.5%) disagreed, and 16 (8.0%) strongly disagreed, revealing that while over half feel appreciated, a considerable number perceive inadequate recognition. For “My supervisor provides guidance without pressure,” 23 respondents (11.5%) strongly agreed, 121 (60.5%) agreed, 35 (17.5%) disagreed, and 21 (10.5%) strongly disagreed, indicating that most employees view their supervisors as supportive rather than coercive. In response to “Under my supervisor's leadership, I perform my work voluntarily,” 23 respondents (11.5%) strongly agreed, 128 (64.0%) agreed, 28 (14.0%) disagreed, and 21 (10.5%) strongly disagreed, implying that the majority of employees are self-motivated under their supervisors' direction. Finally, on “My supervisor's leadership style has impacted my overall job satisfaction,” 28

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respondents (14.0%) strongly agreed, 123 (61.5%) agreed, 26 (13.0%) disagreed, and 23 (11.5%) strongly disagreed, suggesting that leadership style plays a significant role in enhancing overall job satisfaction for most employees.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from research question one revealed that a majority of respondents (69.0%) agreed that they are happy with their current responsibilities in their organisation, indicating a generally positive attitude toward job roles and assigned duties. Furthermore, most respondents (75.0%) agreed that their job inspires them, showing that employees derive motivation and enthusiasm from their work. In addition, a majority (57.5%) agreed that they are willing to put in extra effort to help their organisation succeed, reflecting a strong sense of commitment and dedication among staff. Similarly, 46.0% of respondents agreed that they feel valued at their workplace, suggesting that while many employees experience recognition, there is room for improvement in fostering a deeper sense of value. The findings also revealed that 40.0% of respondents disagreed that they see a future for themselves in the organisation, implying uncertainty about long-term career prospects. Lastly, the majority (59.0%) agreed that the leadership style in their organisation enhances employee engagement, signifying that leadership practices play an important role in motivating and involving employees in organisational activities.

The findings from research question two revealed that a majority of respondents (62.5%) agreed that they feel a sense of accomplishment from their work tasks, suggesting that employees generally find fulfillment in their roles. Similarly, most respondents (63.0%) agreed that their supervisors encourage innovative thinking, indicating that leadership within the organisation supports creativity and new ideas. In terms of recognition, the majority (47.5%) agreed that they are satisfied with the level of acknowledgment they receive for their contributions under their supervisors' leadership, although a notable percentage (28.5%) disagreed, implying room for improvement in employee recognition. Furthermore, 60.5% of respondents agreed that their supervisors provide guidance without pressure, demonstrating a supportive leadership approach. A larger proportion (64.0%) also agreed that they perform their work voluntarily under their supervisors' leadership, showing intrinsic motivation and willingness among employees. Finally, most respondents (61.5%) agreed that their supervisor's leadership style has positively impacted their overall job satisfaction, emphasizing the important role of leadership behaviour in shaping employee attitudes and engagement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that employee engagement and job satisfaction at AGRITED Nigeria Limited are largely influenced by effective leadership practices and positive

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workplace relationships. The results indicated that most employees are happy with their current responsibilities, inspired by their jobs, and willing to put in extra effort toward organisational success. Leadership styles that encourage innovation, provide guidance without undue pressure, and recognize employee contributions were found to enhance motivation, voluntary commitment, and overall job satisfaction. However, the findings also suggested a need for improvement in fostering long-term career prospects and strengthening employees' sense of value and recognition within the organisation. Overall, effective leadership that promotes trust, recognition, and open communication plays a crucial role in sustaining employee engagement and satisfaction.

Recommendations

1. Organisations should strategically adopt diverse leadership styles to foster employee engagement, job satisfaction, loyalty, and retention.
2. Organisations should incorporate transactional leadership elements, such as clear goal-setting and performance-based rewards, to drive productivity and maintain a structured environment.
3. Organisations should invest in leadership development programs aimed at equipping managers with the skills necessary to flexibly implement transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire approaches as appropriate.

Contributions to Knowledge

This research contributed to the understanding of the direct relationship between leadership dynamics, particularly transformational leadership and employee satisfaction and engagement. By demonstrating that transformational leadership significantly enhances job satisfaction and employee engagement, the study provides empirical evidence that supports the growing emphasis on this leadership style as a critical driver of positive organisational outcomes. Also, the study reveals the impact of transactional leadership on employee loyalty, particularly through reward systems, and emphasizes the significance of clear communication and goal setting. This finding adds to the literature by highlighting the potential benefits of transactional leadership in driving employee loyalty, offering a more nuanced understanding of how this leadership style contributes to employee outcomes in organisations where job roles are well-defined. Additionally, the research expanded on the role of laissez-faire leadership by examining its effects on employee retention. The findings suggested that a lack of involvement from leadership in important matters may negatively affect retention, adding to the body of knowledge on the potential drawbacks of this leadership style in organisational settings.

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